

Cerebellar Model Associative Computer (CMAC) for Gravimetric Geoid study based on EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C Geopotential Development

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Abstract— In this paper, cerebellar model associative computer (CMAC) algorithm is proposed to be used for geoid study. This algorithm based on the mapping scheme of input space that transforms input similarity in the input space into associated levels in the associated cells space. Similar inputs mapped to similar levels, while dissimilar inputs associated to mutual independent cells. Associated levels given by overlapping base functions selected represent a subset of “feature” to be parameterized using adaptive linear combiner (ALC) structure where a set of “feature” impersonate as input vector in the back side, parameter or weight vector in the middle side, and an output in the front side. ALC structure adjusts weights value using LMS (least mean square) recursion in the training (or analyzing) session, and accumulates weighted input to get an output in the synthesizing session. Desired output using in weights adjustment are any values from the output space that correspond to respective values in the input space. Model assessment test used to validate CMAC model by comparing residual distance of consecutive points from both EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C geopotential global development is data and respective CMAC model in geocentric coordinates system. By utilization of EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C geopotential global development data sets acquired from selected points of geometric geoid in around of Merapi and Merbabu volcanoes, it is simulated the proposed algorithm to study geoid. The results show that difference between data and model based on EGM96 geopotential global development are about 0.00026296 m in total absolute value with standard deviation about $8.3856 \times 10(6)$ m, and based on EIGEN-GL04C geopotential global development is about 0.00027139 m in total absolute value with standard deviation about 8.5441 m. These results use 1×10^6 epoch in training session with gain factor $\mu = 1.0638 \times 10(4)$ m better result could be achieved by adding more training session with smaller gain factor.

Keywords—cerebellar model associative computer (CMAC), adaptive linear combiner, least mean square, EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C geopotential global development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gravimetric geoid study is a fundamental part in geodesy and other earth sciences in case to define the shape and size of the earth and its gravity field including its temporal variation. Many applications such as EWARS (early warning system) for disaster, oil and gas discovery, land management, and many more, utilize geoid information to

perform specific and dedicated operation in its implementation. This is the facts to be the reason of our study.

One of many tasks in gravimetric study is the modeling of gravimetric geoid that has the same meaning with the surface fitting in which two predicting variables positioned as input and one response variable as the function of two input variables to be an output. For the temporal variation of the surface, we need to add an input time variable, but this is not the case presented here. Related to the surface fitting, there are many research available in text books and references. Most of them use the generalizing of least square method where prior knowledge given in input design suspected as the characteristics of the two-dimensional (2D) plant handled.

In this paper, we propose a gravimetric geoid modeling method that differs with the previous method in the way to incorporate prior knowledge to the modeling system. The method uses an algorithm that exploits the generalization and learning capability of CMAC (cerebellar model associative computer, cerebellar model arithmetic computer, or cerebellar model articulation controller). CMAC is an associative memory neural network based on the mapping scheme of input space that transforms input similarity in the input space into associated levels in the associated cells space. Similar inputs mapped to similar levels, while dissimilar inputs associated to mutual independent cells. CMAC is interpreted as a look up table method [1], and has been used in the areas of control [2]-[6], pattern recognition [7], signal and image processing [8]-[10]. Other research related to the structure and learning of CMAC investigated in [11]-[16].

In the proposed method, CMAC used to learn a non linear mapping from a spatial position into the corresponding geoid value. A geoid position is quantized by a number of quantization levels, and the CMACs input taken from quantizers output, associated to a set of association cells by the input mapping scheme. Training (or analyzing) session uses the association cells and the corresponding geoid value to be a set of respective input and output training. By using the LMS recursion, a set of weights adjusts until a number of epoch reached. Synthesizing session accumulates the weighted inputs to approximate desired output.

II. CMAC

In this section, we give a brief description of CMAC with emphasis on generalization and learning capability. In the proposed method, CMAC is used to learn a nonlinear mapping from a spatial position into the corresponding geoid value. Thus, we limit our discussion to a two-input single-output CMAC, although a general CMAC is capable of learning a multi-input multi-output nonlinear function.

A. Input Mapping Scheme

Let the two-dimensional (2D) input of a nonlinear function be (x,y) , where x and y are a set of L real numbers, $\{x,y\} \in \mathbb{R}^L$, in the closed interval, $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ and $[y_{\min}, y_{\max}]$, respectively. The input x is quantized by 1Q different uniform quantizers with quantization interval 1Q , 1u_i ($i=0,1,2,\dots,U$) where ${}^1u_0 \leq x_{\min}$ and ${}^1u_U \geq x_{\max}$. The pre-superscript "1" used in 1Q and in all symbols in this paper denotes the input dimension. The decision level indexes of 1u_i and ${}^1u_{i+1}$ are given by

$${}^1k = \left\lfloor \frac{x - {}^1u_0}{{}^1u_U - {}^1u_0} ({}^1Q) \right\rfloor + 1 \quad (1)$$

where 1k is a set of L positive integer in interval $[1, {}^1Q]$. The corresponding dequantization levels of (1) are given by

$$\tilde{x} = {}^1u_0 + \frac{2({}^1k)+1}{2({}^1Q)} \times ({}^1u_U - {}^1u_0). \quad (2)$$

Difference between x and \tilde{x} is called the quantization error of the dimension of x . Similarly, the input y is also quantized in the same way as in x . By changing in (1) and in (2), the pre-superscript from "1" to "2", the quantization interval from " u " to " v ", and the index from " M " to " N ", we get a set of L positive integer, 2k , in interval $[1, {}^2Q]$ and the corresponding dequantization levels, \tilde{y} . Difference between y and \tilde{y} is called the quantization error of the dimension of y .

Let the two dimensional (2D) input of CMAC be $({}^1k, {}^2k)$ where 1k and 2k are positive integers in $[1, {}^1Q]$ and $[1, {}^2Q]$ respectively. A set of g address associated by these inputs is given by

$$f_j = p_j + ({}^1f_j) + ({}^1c_j)({}^2f_j), \quad j = 1, \dots, g \quad (3)$$

where

$$p_j = ({}^1c_j)({}^2c_j), \quad (4)$$

$${}^1c_j = \left\lfloor \frac{{}^1Q - {}^1d_j}{g} \right\rfloor + 1, \quad (5)$$

$${}^1f_j = \left\lfloor \frac{{}^1k - {}^1d_j}{g} \right\rfloor, \quad i=1,2. \quad (6)$$

The parameters of CMAC, 1d_j and g , are displacement and generalization parameters, respectively. They are defined

prior the design. Equation (3) gives a number of g address from overall address

$$p = \sum_j p_j. \quad (7)$$

On each associated address, the association levels is defined by

$$a_{k_i,j} = \exp\left(\frac{-(g^2/4)}{({}^i k - (Z_a - 0.5g))((Z_a + 0.5g) - {}^i k)}\right) \quad (8)$$

where Z_a is the center of the covered inputs region in terms of ${}^i k$ ($i=1,2$).

B. Adaptive Linear Combiner (ALC)

The structure of ALC is shown in Fig. 1. There is an input vector, a set of adjustable weights, a summing unit, and a single output. An input vector, \underline{a} , with elements a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p , has a number of g non zero elements where g is integer in the open interval $(0,p)$. These inputs are parameterized by a corresponding sub set of adjustable weights, $w_j \in w$, $j=1, 2, \dots, g$, and summed up by the linear combiner to get a single output, y . The combiner is called "linear" because for a fixed setting of the weights its output is a linear combination of the input components. However, when the weights are in the process of being adjusted, the output of the combiner is no longer a linear function of input. Given an input vector to ALC be in the column form as

$$\underline{a}_n = [a_{1n} \quad a_{2n} \quad \dots \quad a_{pn}]^T \quad (9)$$

Figure 1. Adaptive linear combiner (ALC).

In this notation T stands for transpose so \underline{a}_n is actually a column vector. Any non zero elements in \underline{a}_n , $a_{mn} \neq 0 \in \underline{a}_n$, is given by (8). Here we use both subscript m and n for the element index of input vector and the iteration (and or data presentation) index, respectively. The corresponding set of adjustable weights is also in the column form as

$$\underline{w}_n = [w_{1n} \quad w_{2n} \quad \dots \quad w_{pn}]^T. \quad (10)$$

Given an input vector \underline{a}_n and a weight vector \underline{w}_n , a single output of ALC on the n^{th} iteration is given by

$$y_n = \underline{a}_n^T \underline{w}_n = \sum_{j=1}^g a_{jn} w_{jn} \quad (11)$$

At the first right of equal sign in (11), the overall elements of the weighted input including zero elements is summed up, while in the second one, only g non zero elements to be summed to get the same output, y_n .

C. Learning Scheme and Generalization

The multi input-single output mapping of ALC is determined by the stored weights. The weights are adjusted based on the least mean square algorithm so that the mapping achieves the desired function given a *priori*. Let the output of ALC for the input vector \underline{a} be y , the corresponding training datum be h , and the output error between y and h be ε . Given an input vector \underline{a}_n and the training datum be h_n , the weights w_{jn} ($j=1,2,\dots,g$) associated with the input are adjusted according to

$$w_{j(n+1)} = w_{jn} + \delta_{jn}; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, g \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_j &= 2\mu\varepsilon_n a_{jn} \\ \varepsilon_n &= h_n - y_n \end{aligned}$$

The parameter μ is a gain factor that governs a learning speed. Let the output error for the input \underline{a}_n after the updating be ε^+ . Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_n^+ &= h_n - \underline{a}_n^T (\underline{w}_n + 2\mu\varepsilon_n \underline{a}_n) \\ &= h_n - y_n - 2\mu\varepsilon_n \underline{a}_n^T \underline{a}_n \\ &= (1 - 2\mu \underline{a}_n^T \underline{a}_n) \varepsilon_n. \end{aligned}$$

To make $|\varepsilon_n^+| \leq |\varepsilon_n|$, the parameter μ is selected so it is in the interval

$$0 < \mu \leq \frac{1}{2 \underline{a}_n^T \underline{a}_n} \quad (13)$$

The significant feature of CMAC is that the learning scheme changes the output values for the nearby inputs, because each of subregions that formed by $a_{mn} \in \underline{a}_n$ covers g^2 inputs, ${}^i k$ ($i=1,2$). Therefore, similar inputs lead to similar outputs even for untrained inputs. This property is called generalization, which is of great use in the CMAC-based modelling. Moreover, we can control the degree of generalization by changing the size of g . A larger g gives larger subregion and wider generalization region. This is to be the reason so g is called a generalization parameter.

Fig. 2(a) shows the generalization region of CMAC with $g=4$. We shall give a training signal to the input $h(5,6)$. The input then specifies four subregions denoted by the squares, and four weights stored in the subregions are updated. The number of updated weights for each input is represented by “1”, “2”, “3”, and “4”. The outputs indicated by “4”, “3”,

Figure 2. Generalization property of CMAC. (a) $g=4$. (b) $g=2$.

“2”, and “1” are increased by $(2\mu\varepsilon a_j)$, $(3\mu\varepsilon a_j/2)$, $(\mu\varepsilon a_j)$, and $(\mu\varepsilon a_j/2)$, respectively, where ε is the output error for the input (5,6) before the updating and a_j is the corresponding association levels with respect to the covered inputs $({}^1 k, {}^2 k)$. We see that the CMAC outputs are changed even for untrained inputs. For comparison, Fig. 2(b) shows the generalization region of a CMAC with $g=2$. In this case, two weights are updated, and the outputs indicated by “2” and “1” are increased by $(2\mu\varepsilon a_j)$ and $(\mu\varepsilon a_j)$, respectively. We see that the generalization region becomes smaller than the previous one.

III. CMAC-BASED MODELING

Fig. 3 shows a structure of the proposed modelling system. Here, an input pair (x,y) is quantized by an interval quantizer to get a quantized quantity pair, $({}^1 k, {}^2 k)$. The input mapping uses both ${}^1 k$ and ${}^2 k$ to generate the association address, m . Those quantized quantity pair is also utilized to calculate the association levels in m address, \underline{a}_m . ALC then uses the association levels \underline{a}_m and an output h to be its training data pair. After a set of weights adjusted in the training session of ALC, the association levels weighted by a fixed set of weights is summed up to get an approximation of the desired output, \tilde{h} . Because of using a quantized quantity pair in the input mapping, the dequantizer then needs to dequantize them to get the quantized input, \tilde{x} and \tilde{y} , that corresponds to the output \tilde{h} in $\tilde{h}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$.

Figure 3. Generalization property of CMAC. (a) $g=4$. (b) $g=2$.

The gravimetric geoid data can be represented in general form as $h(x,y)$ where the spatial position, x and y , is referred to longitude and latitude, respectively, and the gravimetric geoid, h , is the geoid height at position (x,y) . Given a set of L positions, $\{x,y\} \in \mathbb{R}^L$, where x in $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ and y in $[y_{\min}, y_{\max}]$. Let the selected ROI (region of interest) for the dimension of x and y be in interval $[^1u_0, ^1u_M]$ and $[^1v_0, ^1v_N]$ respectively so the ROI covers all position in datasets. By deciding a number of 1Q and 2Q quantization levels for each of ROI intervals, quantizer (1) will give a set of L positive integer $\{^1k, ^2k\}$ where 1k in $[1, ^1Q]$ and 2k in $[1, ^2Q]$. Equation (3) then utilized those quantized quantities, 1k and 2k , to associate a number of g address vector as the element indexes of $\underline{a}_n \in \mathbb{R}^p$ ($n=1,2,\dots,L$). Those quantized quantities are also used by (8) to calculate the corresponding association levels in each associated address. ALC then uses both association vector \underline{a}_n and geoid height h be its input-output training. By selecting a gain factor, μ , so it is in (13), a set of adjustable weights, $w \in \mathbb{R}^p$, is trained by ALC using (12) until some stopping criteria achieved. Given a fixed set of adjusted weights, $w^* \in \mathbb{R}^p$, and an association vector, $\underline{a}_n \in \mathbb{R}^p$, $n=1,2,\dots,L$, an approximation of geoid height, \tilde{h}_n , is calculated by (11). The quantity \tilde{h}_n is not only an approximation value of *true* geoid height h_n , but its corresponding position, (\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) , given by dequantizer (2) is also an approximation value of *true* position (x,y) .

The last statements in the previous paragraph confirms the using of model assesment that incorporate the approximated values in both \tilde{h} and (\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) . Reference [17] was given a respective procedure in model assesment that used by this paper. In that procedure, data and model in geodetic coordinat system are transformed into geocentric cartesian system and then distance of consecutive points in the new coordinat system are calculated. Residual distances between model and data are used to asses the model.

As shown in Fig. 2, generalization regions can be control by using a pre-defined value of generalization parameter, g . In "unpublished" [18], generalization g is pre-defined so it is a positive integer in $[1, \max(^1Q, ^2Q)]$. By first plotting the distribution of TTG (*tanda tinggi geodesi*) to see its coverage area and defining properly ROI so it covers all TTG, then generalization g is approximately defined in such so its value is equal or larger than the maximum distance between the ROI frames and its respective TTG area frames. For comparing purpose in this paper, we implement two CMACs with different generalization parameter in the same maximum quantization level of both x and y . Here we define CMAC with $g=73$ and $g=123$ in the maximum quantization level $^1Q=^2Q=256$.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the distribution of TTG points around Merapi and Merbabu volcanoes are first explained. Those TTGs are then processed by the proposed method and the results which are consist of contour lines of corresponding geoid heights model given by two CMACs with different g , will be discussed in the second part of this section. Model assesments are then presented in the last part and also closed this section.

Fig. 4(a) and (b) show the distribution of TTG points and its corresponding EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C geoid height, respectively. In geoid height plotting, difference of geoids by its minimum value are used instead of its original one to visually enhance its spatial distribution of geoid in each TTG. In those figures we then know that TTGs which are lie in the path from Surakarta to Yogyakarta, are mostly have minimal geoid heights, while TTGs which are lained in the path from around Muntilan to near Ambarawa are mostly have maximal and uniform geoid heights. Different with

Figure 4. Distribution of TTG and its corresponding geoid height, (a) EGM96, (b) EIGEN-GL04C.

Figure 5. Contour lines of geoid model and difference between geoid data and its model using CMAC with $g=73$, (a) EGM96, (b) EIGEN-Gl.04C.

Figure 6. Contour lines of geoid model and difference between geoid data and its model using CMAC with $g=123$, (a) EGM96, (b) EIGEN-Gl.04C.

TTGs in two paths explained previously, TTGs which are lained in the path from Bawen to Boyolali are have fluctuative geoid heights.

Fig. 5 and 6 show contour lines of geoid models which are given by CMAC with $g=73$ and $g=123$, respectively. In both figures, EGM96 model are placed in the up side, while another one are in the bottom side. All figures use the same resolution in contour lines calculating, that is, a number of 64 contour levels is defined on peak-to peak values of geoid model. Those figures show that the geoid models given by CMAC with smaller g has more peaks (top and bottom) than others in geoid models given by CMAC with larger g . CMAC with smaller g generalize a small area around trained points and a narrow valley at near the volcanoes shown in Fig. 5(a) and (b) is caused by the overlapping of generalization regions is only in their edges. Different situations as shown in Fig. 6(a) and (b) are given by CMAC with larger g . In this situations, generalization regions which almost covered all trained points are functioned as a *bridge*

of extrapolating points to share their “knowledge” received from respective trained points. Vertical lines that figured on each TTGs in Fig. 5 and 6 are difference between geoid data and its model. From those lines we visually know that CMAC with smaller g has a smaller difference. This visually assesment will be explored quantitatively in the next discussion.

Fig. 7 and 8 show the results of model assesment procedure related to the geoid model displaying on Fig. 5 and 6, respectively. In that procedure, distance of consequite points in geocentric cartesian system are calculated from both data and model. Residual distance which are defined as difference distance between data and model are then used to asses the model. As we have expected, CMAC with smaller g has smaller residual distance than other ones given by CMAC with larger g . For CMAC with $g=73$, residual distance of EGM96 model is about 0.00025 m in total absolut value and standard deviation is about 7.47×10^{-6} m. These two values are lower

than another ones given by CMAC with $g=123$. This CMAC produces EGM96 model with residual distance is about 0.00069 m and standard deviation is about 1.94×10^{-5} m. Fig. 7 and 8 are also showed that using the same CMAC, residual distance that was given by EIGEN-GL04C models is larger then it was given by EGM96 models.

Figure 7. Model assesment in using CMAC with $g=73$

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, it is presented that CMAC was a method to propose gravimetric geoid using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C geopotential developments. The advantages of the proposed method are summarized as follows.

- 1) It is very well in local gravimetric geoid response.
- 2) It does not need to redesign when the datasets updated.
- 3) Spatial resolution is known and customized before the development process, even if the datasets are limited.

CMAC is inherently capable of learning a multi-input multi-output non linear function. Using three input single output CMAC's, the proposed method for 2D non linear function can straightforwardly be applied to 3D system such as temporal variation of 2D gravity field. The extension will be shown elsewhere.

Figure 8. Model assesment in using CMAC with $g=123$

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